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**An Assessment of Intergovernmental
Collaboration towards Primary
Healthcare Delivery and Management
Challenges in Osun State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

Inter-governmental collaboration is the collaborative efforts of several governmental levels to accomplish shared objectives. The study assessed

intergovernmental collaboration in primary health care delivery in Osun State with emphasis on the key management challenges conforing the coordination and administration of primary health care delivery. The study adopted both primary and secondary sources of data collection. Primary data were obtained through structured questionnaires, while secondary data were sourced from relevant policy documents and official health sector reports. Findings from the study revealed that lack of political will ($\bar{x} = 4.20$), inadequate inter-sectoral collaboration ($\bar{x} = 4.02$), and inadequate funding and misappropriation of funds ($\bar{x} = 3.90$) constituted major challenges confronting intergovernmental collaboration in the management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State. The results further showed a statistically significant relationship between intergovernmental collaboration and the management of primary healthcare delivery ($r = 0.384$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that collaboration between the three levels of government is crucial to Osun State's efficient administration of primary healthcare services. It is therefore recommended that, in order to improve primary healthcare delivery and foster effective collaboration, the study's key management challenges, such as lack of political will, inadequate funding, misappropriation, inter-sectoral partnership, and other challenges identified, must be addressed.

Keywords: Intergovernmental, Primary Health Care, Health Care, Delivery, Local Government

Introduction

Intergovernmental collaboration entails the collective involvement of several tiers of government to work together on shared goals, policies, or services (Bello-Gomez & Cheng, 2024). It is a process where various levels of government collaborate on common objectives that are crucial to the existence of a country (Bello, 2014). These objectives include: health, education, development, and economic growth that involve the sharing of resources, coordinating efforts and negotiating responsibilities. Intergovernmental collaboration survives in a federal form of government, and as such, it is inevitable because the growth of such a country primarily rests on the combined efforts of the several levels of government (Gamb& Ibrahim, 2024) It described organised procedures and patterns that governmental tiers employed to involve other tiers, non-governmental stakeholders in creating and executing government policies, and the provision of public services (Adedeji, 2025).

Intergovernmental collaboration in primary health care (PHC) addresses the joint participation of different levels of government in PHC for equitable

service delivery, sustainable development and improved health outcomes, which are all dependent on effective governance (Taleat, 2019). Nigeria is a highly populous nation with many complex social, political, and economic facets. The provision of basic health care presents considerable difficulties, ranging from inconsistent policy execution, insufficient infrastructure, lack of workers and dispersed service delivery (Croke & Ogbuoji, 2024). The country explicitly recognises that there should be collaborative efforts towards the health sector, to encourage equitable access to healthcare, and the health sector was included in the concurrent legislative list. The federal, state, and local governments have related duties to fulfil for their constituents. There is a spirit of cooperation across the various levels of government in delivering health care services to enhance Nigerians' quality of life while also producing revenue for the government (Taleat, 2019).

Intergovernmental Collaboration

The terms intergovernmental and collaboration are two distinct concepts. The term intergovernmental refers to a variety of interactions or activities that span numerous levels of government, including federal, state, and local. Contrarily, collaboration is the process by which two or more entities work together to complete a task or achieve a shared goal; in essence, it involves combining resources, ideas, and expertise to achieve desired outcomes. Intergovernmental collaboration is the process by which various governmental levels, national, state, and local, collaborate on common objectives, combining resources and knowledge to solve complicated issues, provide services effectively, and develop unified policies. It transcends barriers to coordinate efforts on issues including public health, economic reforms and sustainability.

In numerous works of literature on public administration and governance, the term intergovernmental collaboration has been used interchangeably with intergovernmental relations, which describes the relationship between the government's arms and parastatals in carrying out their current and residual responsibilities (Daryl, 2013). Intergovernmental collaboration is a synergy in the form of delegation, decentralisation, allocation of resources, distribution of responsibilities, federation of roles, and mechanisms for interaction among government tiers, agencies, and/or levels of authority (Meiling, Xing, Mengqiu, Enrica, Xiaoxian, 2021). Intergovernmental collaboration is requisite to increase capacities and enhance role cooperation

in public institutions such as health (public and primary health facilities), education (public secondary and elementary schools), etc.

Intergovernmental relations are a crucial element of every political system with many levels of government; collaboration is essential for governments to provide services effectively and efficiently. Intergovernmental collaboration aims to achieve shared objectives through mutual ties and across vertical and horizontal governmental arrangements, alignment, and cohesiveness throughout all areas of government (Tshishonga, 2017). The goal of intergovernmental relations is to support democracy and enhance delivery capacity across all branches of government for the common good by facilitating the execution of government activities, particularly service delivery, through synergy, efficiency, and effectiveness in service delivery (Ile, 2010). These cooperative efforts are crucial in Nigeria because the 1999 Constitution allows for the necessary coordination and cooperation between different governmental levels in the provision of essential public services that are, according to the constitution, their shared responsibilities, since no level has the exclusive functional right to service delivery on its own.

Primary Health Care

Primary health care is a comprehensive and all-encompassing approach to healthcare delivery that focuses on meeting the local health needs of people, families, and communities. One of the most significant fundamental papers on primary health care is the Alma-Ata Declaration, which was adopted at the 1978 International Conference on Primary Health Care. The proclamation emphasised the necessity of primary health care as a fundamental right for every person to attain universal health, which requires intersectoral collaboration, community participation, and tackling the socioeconomic determinants of health (WHO, 1978). Furthermore, the commitment to primary health care as a means of achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and universal health coverage was reaffirmed in the Alma-Ata Declaration, which was agreed upon during the 2018 Global Conference on Primary Health Care. Health promotion, person-centred care, and robust primary healthcare systems were emphasised (WHO, 2019).

PHC's basic belief is that everyone, everywhere, has the right to achieve optimal health. PHC is a comprehensive approach to effectively organising and supporting national health systems to bring wellness and health

services closer to communities. The three components are as follows: Individuals, families, and communities, who are empowered to take charge of their own health throughout their lives through integrated health services that address the larger causes of good health through comprehensive policies and activities (WHO, 2019). Primary health care is the provision of basic medical treatment at a cost that the community and the country can afford to sustain at every level of development, and it is made available to all individuals and families in the community via full involvement. It is founded on technology and processes that are socially acceptable, scientifically validated, and practicable (University of Cape Town, 2025).

PHC is a strategy for healthcare that promotes everyone's attainment of a state of health that will allow them to live socially and economically fulfilling lives. PHC stands for essential, moral, affordable, readily available, fair, rational and community-accountable healthcare (WHO,1978). It is not only basic or preventive treatment, nor is it a set of cheap medical interventions for the underprivileged in society. PHC encourages the inclusion of medical care into the scheme of community development, which necessitates community engagement, intersectoral collaboration, and political commitment for sustainability.

An Overview of Nigeria's Healthcare System: The Nature, Structure, and Collaboration of Nigerian Healthcare Service Delivery

Nigeria's healthcare system is constitutionally and formally acknowledged at three levels: primary, secondary, and tertiary (Revised National Health Policy, 1998; The Amended 1999 Constitution; the 2014 National Health Act). PHC offers patients first, non-critical medical care. It attends to the prompt treatment of patients with typhoid, malaria, fever, children's illnesses, stomach disorders, newborns, neonatal, and maternity issues, and immunisation of children against polio and other illnesses (Ademiluyi & Aluko-Arowolo, 2009). PHC service centres primarily address minor and non-critical health issues, raise community awareness on health issues, handle family planning issues, employ medical equipment, infrastructure, and expertise to treat common illnesses. PHC facilities keep local health records, especially complicated cases that they cannot handle, and report and refer patients to secondary healthcare centres.

Secondary healthcare centres handle prevention and treat not too common cases (FMOH, 2001). Comprehensive health centres and general hospitals are part of secondary centres. Where there are complicated cases that cannot be handled by the centres, such cases are referred to the tertiary or specialised hospitals. The second level of healthcare is expected to be equipped with at least three medical doctors, beds, and facilities adequate for at least 30 patients. It should also make provisions for facilities to diagnose and treat ailments (WHO, 2006). Furthermore, it offers surgery and provides some pediatric and obstetric services (Badru, 2003). Secondary health centres are often built in the cities or the state capitals (Ademiluyi *et al.* 2009).

The tertiary healthcare centres are owned by the federal government, and they are also known as teaching hospitals. They are established to provide intervention to complex health issues admitted from secondary health centres or directly. They are expected to have sophisticated equipment and infrastructure for diagnosis and treatments, as well as the capacity to conduct health research that will inform health policies (Ademiluyi *et al.* 2009). They are officially recognised for the teaching of medical courses and training of health personnel. They are expected to be equipped with a large number of skilled workforce and specialists who render standard health services.

PHC is controlled by the third-tier government, but it is generally overseen by the state ministry of health in conjunction with the National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA). Also, both the federal and state governments fund the PHC since the local government is not completely financially independent to do so. Secondary healthcare is controlled by the state governments but under the co-supervision of both the state and the Federal Ministry of Health (Igbokwe, Ibrahim, Aina, Umar, Salihu, Omoregie, and Aigbogun, 2024). That is, it is the state governments that fund secondary health centres as well as control the state university teaching hospitals. And tertiary healthcare is managed and controlled by the federal government through FMOH. Following the division, healthcare facilities are categorised based on the responsibilities designated to the above-mentioned levels of healthcare arrangement. Precisely, the teaching (general) hospitals across Nigeria, as well as federal medical centres, are categorised under tertiary healthcare and thus financed and controlled by the federal government. State medical facilities and hospitals constitute

secondary healthcare and are thus governed by the state government, whereas primary health clinics are managed by local governments (Federal Ministry of Health and Social Welfare, 2025).

Nigeria's healthcare system is well-coordinated, but the roles of various governmental levels clearly overlap. In recent years, this has led to effective education on current health issues and strategies for prevention and management, promotion of adequate food and nutritional access, the provision of clean water and essential sanitation facilities, medical care for maternal and child well-being, including contraceptive services, immunisation against major infectious diseases, early detection and management of local disease outbreaks, proper treatment of common illnesses and injuries, and availability of necessary medications (Yisa, Ogunniyi, and Dine, 2025).

The Operation of Primary Healthcare in Nigeria

PHC was coined at a health-related conference organised by the World Health Organisation and United Nations Children's Fund at Alma-Ata, Soviet Union, and which was attended by representatives of over 100 countries (Sebayang, 2023). The conference addressed health discourses across national, regional, and global concerns. Numerous health studies refer to the conference's resolutions as the Alma-Ata Declaration. The declaration defined primary healthcare as crucial healthcare based on workable, scientifically sound, and socially acceptable methods and technology that are universally accessible to individuals and families in the community and are affordable to maintain at every stage of their development (World Health Organisation, 1978). As outlined by WHO (1987), the aim and objectives are to address the health issues producing the greatest rates of death and disability at a cost that the community can afford, make health services accessible to everyone, regardless of where they live or work, ensure that the community are actively involved in the planning, execution, and evaluation of health programmes in spirit of self-reliance (World Health Organisation, 1978).

The health components outlined by the Alma-Ata Declaration as the focus of the PHC are health education and sensitisation towards preventing health problems; supply of nutritional food; provision of consumable water and sanitation; maternal and infant healthcare; family planning inclusive; immunisation programs, prevention and control of endemics; drug

provision; and promotion of mental health. With the contents of the Alma-Ata Declaration, the PHC centres are recognised in the National Health Policy of Nigeria to carry out services and provide first-contact health services to prevent, cure and promote good health practices through health sensitisation and education. The standard health services of the PHC centres in Nigeria are also found in the Ward Minimum Health Care Package, which is the guideline for the delivery of PHC to wards at all local government levels (World Health Organisation, 2017).

PHC facilities are primarily an extension of an LGA, thus making the committees in charge of wards, as well as the health department of the local government, take primary contact with the PHCs. Given the nature of its structure, staffing, equipment, services rendered and ownership (World Health Organisation, 2017). PHC facilities assume different nomenclatures such as dispensaries, health clinics, health centres, primary health centres, maternity, health posts, and comprehensive health centres, whereas the ward health system wishes to acknowledge three terms: primary health clinics, health posts, and primary healthcare centres (NPHCDA, 2004). While several such facilities are government-owned, some are privately-owned (e.g., clinics and medical centres owned by churches, medical professionals like doctors and pharmacists, etc.), as well as a few others established by NGOs and civil society organisations.

Primary Healthcare Facilities and Collaborative Responsibilities of Stakeholders

Primary healthcare centres (PHCs) are the initial point for interaction with the healthcare system. To ensure that PHCs are operational, accessible, and in line with community needs, multistakeholder engagement is crucial to their successful operation. There is but a somewhat complex relationship in the roles of government levels, as well as that of partners/agencies to keep PHCs running, and even so, the roles and the way they are structured vary by state. These assigned responsibilities are required because there is no single level of government or organisation in charge of funding, overseeing, and managing health care services (Odutolu, Ihebuzor, Tilley-Gyado, Martufi, Ajuluchukwu, Olubajo, and Muhammad, 2016). The diagram below is an example of a structure including the agencies participating in the delivery of PHC services.

Figure 1: An example of Government Agencies with Responsibilities in PHC
Source: Bonilla Chacin, Okigbo, Malife, Sherburne Benz, and Ruhl (2010)

- i. NYSC- National Youth Service Corps
- ii. NPHCDA- National Primary Health Care Development Agency
- iii. FMOH- the Federal Ministry of Health;
- iv. PHCDA- Primary Health Care Development Area;
- v. SMOH- State Ministry of Health;
- vi. SMLGA- State Ministry of Local Government Area
- vii. SRDC- State Rural Development Commission;
- viii. DPHC- Department of Primary Health Care;
- ix. LGSC- Local Government Service Commission

LGAs oversee and provide the usual financial responsibilities needed at PHC facilities. Also, the health departments of the LGAs manage the PHC facilities. However, each level of government creates and carries out its agenda within the ambience of PHC. The federal government, the FMOH and the NPHCDA institute guides for the system of PHC in Nigeria, while the guide for the operation of the Ward Health System is overseen by the FMOH. The funds for these occasional programs are covered in the federal

budget. Besides, the state can also decide to create a health operational policy and see that it works even up to the PHC levels (Gyuse, Ayuk, and Okeke, 2018).

The state ministries of local government (SMLG) can institute guidelines on health matters that affect the PHC. Additionally, the local government service board or commission (LGSB or LGSC) can offer management recommendations for the LG workforce, which includes PHC employees. The Local Government Service Commission, the Civil Service Commission, the Ministry of Budget and Planning, state hospitals management boards, faith-based organisations, nongovernmental organisations, zonal and state offices of the National Primary Health Care Development Agency, FMOH, the National Health Insurance Scheme, and state ministries of health and local government affairs are among the notable agencies and organisations that are involved in addition to the primary effort of the local government in managing the PHC facilities.

Statement of Problem

The decentralisation of health services insinuates that at the federal level, a ministry called the Ministry of Health (FMOH) should manage the country's health, develop initiatives, and set policy (Eboreime, Abimbola, Obi, Ebirim, Olubajo, Eyles, & Mambulu, 2017). The State governments are responsible for implementing health care policy at the basic, secondary and tertiary health centres (Taleat, 2019). The breakdown of each of the roles that each level of government performs is accentuated by the FMOH, the ministry makes policy, articulates strategies and coordinates the nation's health, while the state is saddled with policy implementation at the primary, secondary and tertiary health centres (Omoleke, 2010). The idea of primary health care as a means of coordinating medical intervention for people at the local level is not new; it dates back to the Alma-Ata Declaration of 1978 (Dada, 2023). PHC is anticipated to function through the cooperative duties of the federal, state, and local governments. However, the system continues to suffer from persistent challenges that are a result of significant shortcomings in intergovernmental collaboration and essential management strategies. The current level of engagement in Osun State's primary healthcare system under Governor Ademola Adeleke's administration is being evaluated to meet the World Health Organisation standard by revamping PHC facilities to run continuously. Solar energy or

other alternative power sources are used to supply water and electricity, and the Osun Primary Healthcare Board assists with the provision of drugs (Osun State Official Website, 2024).

Despite the creation of national policies, state-level reforms, and local implementation frameworks, the three levels of government have not effectively collaborated, which has led to overlapping responsibilities, uneven policy implementation, and disjointed decision-making processes. Accountability systems are still inadequate, and funding transfers are frequently insufficient or delayed. Primary healthcare institutions are directly managed by local governments, which sometimes lack the administrative skills, independence, and resources necessary to function well (Taleat, 2019). The population's access to vital health services is compromised by a cycle of inefficiency brought on by these administrative and governance deficiencies. Lingering managerial challenges, including poor coordination, inadequate leadership structures, unclear lines of authority, weak monitoring and evaluation, inadequate funding, lack of effective collaboration, overlapping roles, fragmented decision making, inefficient human resources, and limited intergovernmental communication, are at the heart of the nation's primary healthcare centres' ongoing struggles with poor service quality (Obembe, 2024). These issues lead to ongoing shortages of qualified healthcare professionals, inconsistent medicine supply, decaying infrastructure, and a decline in public trust in the primary healthcare system.

Nevertheless, there is a lack of research on a critical assessment of a specific state government's management of health services in the Southwest to determine the degree to which this government has been able to maintain medical intervention at the local level in accordance with the directives to implement health programs through cooperative efforts of the state, its local governments, and international/local non-governmental organisations. As a result, the focus of this study is on the cooperative efforts of the federal government, the Osun State Government, local governments, and non-governmental players, as well as the analysis of the major management issues that arise while providing healthcare services.

Research Question

What are the key management challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on the management of primary healthcare system in Osun State?

Objectives of the Study

Analyse the key management challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of primary healthcare system in Osun State.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey; the study elicited data using a structured questionnaire. A sample size of 299 comprises (266) survey citizens, five (5) Doctors, seven (7) Nurses, five (5) pharmacists, seven (7) community health workers, five (5) Untrained Informal Healthcare service providers, and three (3) Ministry of Health personnel were selected for administration of questionnaire using Krejcie and Morgans Statistical Formula. The data gathered were analysed using inferential statistical instruments.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents' Characteristics

Respondents			
Characteristics	Frequency	Per cent	Cumulative Percent
Age			
21 – 30	54	18.1	18.1
31 - 40	63	21.1	39.2
41 – 50	137	45.9	85.1
51 & above	45	15.1	100.0
Total	299	100.0	
Sex			
Male	37	12.4	12.4
Female	262	87.6	100.0
Total	299	100.0	
Education Background			

School Leaving Certificate	0	0.0	
WASSCE/SSCE/GCE	37	12.4	0.0
CE	187	62.5	12.4
OND/DIP/MIDWIFERY	75	25.1	74.9
B.Sc. Others	0	0.0	100.0
Total	299	100.0	
Years of experience			
1-5 years	48	16.1	16.1
6-10 years	134	44.8	60.9
11 years and above	117	39.1	100.0
Total	299	100.0	
Grade Level			
Senior	107	35.8	35.8
Junior	192	64.2	100.0
Total	299	100.0	
Local Government			
Ife Central	54	18.1	18.1
Atakumosa East	49	16.4	34.5
Ede South	51	17.1	51.6
Ayedaade	45	15.1	66.7
Olorunda	53	17.7	84.4
Odo-Otin	47	15.7	100.0
Total	299	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2: Key Management Challenges Confronting the Intergovernmental Collaboration on Management of Primary Healthcare System in Osun State

S/N	Assertions	Strongly Agree		Strongly Disagree		No Response	Descriptive Statistics
		f (%)	f (%)	f (%)	f (%)		
i.	Lack of political will	107 (23.4)	134 (44.8)	32 (10.7)	19 (6.4)	2 (0.7)	4.20

	Inadequate funding/misappropriation of funds	70 (23.4)	158 (52.8)	49 (16.4)	2 (0.7)	3.90
ii.				12 (4.0)		
	Inadequate inter-sectoral collaboration	123 (41.1)	96 (32.1)	3 (1.0)	2 (0.7)	4.02
iii.				24 (8.0)		
	Conflicts between Local and State Governments	138 (46.2)	124 (41.5)	3 (1.0)	6 (2.0)	3.78
iv.				26 (8.7)		
	Community perceptions of poor quality and inadequacy of available services in the PHC centres	123 (41.1)	140 (46.8)	10 (3.3)	2 (0.7)	3.98
v.				19 (6.4)		
	Under/low utilization of PHC services	142 (47.5)	119 (39.8)	12 (4.0)	2 (0.7)	3.77
vi				21 (7.0)		

Vii	Poor community participation	87 (29.1)	72 (24.1)	82 (27.4)	52 (17.4)	1 (0.3)	3.14
Viii	Lack of motivation in the workplace, including poor remuneration	68 (22.7)	101 (33.8)	26 (8.7)	97 (32.4)	1 (0.3)	3.26
Ix	Noninvolvement of the private health sector in the planning and implementation of PHC	59 (19.7)	122 (40.8)	55 (18.4)	57 (19.1)	1 (0.3)	3.16
X	Heavy dependence on initiatives funded by foreign donors like UNICEF and USAID	61 (20.4)	125 (41.8)	34 (11.4)	72 (24.1)	3 (1.0)	3.24

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Results

Key Management Challenges Confronting the Intergovernmental Collaboration on Management of Primary Healthcare System in Osun State

This section focuses on the results gathered from the study on the assessment of intergovernmental collaboration towards primary healthcare delivery and management challenges in Osun State. Respondents were asked to score each of the statements set out to analyse the assessment of intergovernmental collaboration towards primary healthcare delivery and management challenges in Osun State. The values/responses of the

statements were categorised using a Likert scale, such as: Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Strongly Disagree (2) and Disagree (1). Furthermore, qualitative data analysis was employed to supplement quantitative research to have a thorough discussion. Furthermore, the mean value (\bar{X}) reflects the respondent's strength for each of the claims, using the following decision rule: where ($\bar{X} < 3.0$), more respondents were inclined to disagree; and where ($\bar{X} > 3.0$), more respondents tended to agree. As shown in Table 2, the first assertion to assess key management challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State was the lack of political will. The respondents were asked to rate how satisfied or dissatisfied they are with the governmental factor in the state when it comes to the lack of political will. In their responses, 107 respondents (23.4%) strongly agreed with the argument, with a similar trend of 134 respondents (44.8%) agreeing. Only 32 (10.7%) of respondents strongly disagreed with the assertion, while 19 (6.4%) disagreed. This frequency distribution was corroborated by the mean and standard deviation ($\bar{X} = 4.20$, $SD = 0.971$). The interpretation of this distribution is that the lack of political will has remarkably been responsible for the challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on the management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State.

The second assertion to assess key management challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State was that inadequate funding/misappropriation of funds was a key management challenge. In the respondent's reactions, 49 (16.4%) of the respondents and 12 (4.0%) of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively; while 70 (23.4%) of the respondents and 158 representing 58.2% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively. This data distribution shows that a reasonable number of the respondents appear to have agreed with the assertion that inadequate funding/misappropriation of funds has been responsible for the challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State, as verified through the mean value and standard deviation ($\bar{X} = 3.90$, $SD = 0.867$).

The third assertion to assess key management challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State was that inadequate inter-sectoral collaboration is a

key management challenge. It was reported that 123 (41.1%) of the respondents strongly agreed with the fact that inadequate inter-sectoral collaboration is another key management challenge responsible for confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State. While 96 representing 32.1% of the respondents, only agreed with the statement. However, 51 (17.1%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with the position that inadequate inter-sectoral collaboration is one of the key management challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State, and 24 (8.0%) of the respondents believed to have disagreed with the position. This implies that inadequate inter-sectoral collaboration is one of the key management challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State, since the mean value (4.02) is beyond the mid-point of 3.0.

As depicted in Table 2, the respondents were asked whether conflicts between local and state governments are mostly observed as the key management challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State. In their reaction, 138 representing 46.2% of the respondents strongly agreed, and 124 (41.1%) of the respondents agreed with this position. However, 3 (1.0%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with the assertion that conflicts between local and state governments are mostly observed as the challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State, while 26, representing 8.7% of the respondents, disagreed with the assertion. Unlike the other respondents, 6 representing 2.0% of the respondents took a neutral position on this assertion. This rather implies that conflicts between local and state governments are another key management challenge confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State, as verified by the mean value and standard deviation ($\bar{X} = 3.78$, $SD = 0.992$).

In addition, the table reported that 123 (41.1%) of the respondents rated the assertion that community perceptions of poor quality and inadequacy of available services in the PHC centres with a strong agreement, while 140, representing 46.8% of the respondents, only supported the assertion. However, 10 (3.3%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with the position

that community perceptions of poor quality and inadequacy of available services in the PHC centres were seen as the key management challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State, and 19 (6.4%) of the respondents believed to have disagreed with the position. This implies that community perceptions of poor quality and inadequacy of available services in the PHC centres are seen as the factor responsible for the challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration, and the mean value (3.98) is beyond the mid-point of 3.0. This confirms that community perceptions of poor quality and inadequacy of available services in the PHC centres are seen as the challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State, with the mean value and standard deviation ($\bar{X} = 3.98$, $SD = 1.027$).

Respondents were asked whether low utilisation of PHC services is another key management challenge responsible for confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State. In their different reactions to the assertion, 142 (47.5%) of the respondents strongly agreed with this assertion, and 119, representing 39.8% of the respondents, agreed with this assertion. However, 12 respondents, representing 4.0% of the respondents, strongly disagreed with this assumption that low utilisation of PHC services is not responsible for the challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State. While 21 (7.0%) disagreed with the assumption. It was a remarkable agreement level with the assertion, as shown by the result of the analysis, though with either little disagreement or indecision by 11.0% of the respondents. This confirms that low utilisation of PHC services is another key management challenge responsible for confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State, through the mean value and standard deviation ($\bar{X} = 3.91$, $SD = 0.906$).

As presented in Table 2, the following distributions were observed when respondents were asked whether poor community participation is another key management challenge confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State. In the respondents' various reactions, 87 (29.1%) of the respondents strongly agreed to this claim, while 72 (24.1%) of the respondents agreed. However, 82 representing 27.4% of the respondents strongly disagreed with the

position that poor community participation has led to challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State and 52 (17.4%) of the respondents were believed to have disagreed with this claim. This distribution implies that poor community participation has led to challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State; the mean value ($\bar{X} = 3.14$, $SD = 1.532$) as well as standard deviation ($\bar{X} = 3.14$, $SD = 1.532$) confirm this.

Also, 68 (22.7%) and 101 (33.8%) of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed, respectively, that lack of motivation in the workplace, including poor remuneration, has significantly contributed to the challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in the study area. However, another 26 representing 8.7% of the respondents and 97 (32.4%) strongly disagreed and disagreed with the position lack of motivation in the workplace, including poor remuneration, has significantly contributed to the challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in the study area. This rather implies that lack of motivation in the workplace, including poor remuneration, has significantly contributed to the challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in the study area. The mean value and standard deviation ($\bar{X} = 3.26$, $SD = 1.275$) confirm this.

On the contrary, it was reported that 55 (18.4%) of the respondents and 57 (19.1%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively, on the assumption that the non-involvement of the private health sector in the planning and implementation of PHC has contributed to challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in the study area. However, 59 (19.7%) of the respondents strongly agreed with the assumption, while 122, representing 40.8% of the respondents, agreed with this position that non-involvement of the private health sector in the planning and implementation of PHC has contributed to challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration on management of the primary healthcare system in the study area. This implies that the non-involvement of the private health sector in the planning and implementation of PHC has contributed to challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration and management of the

primary healthcare system in the study area, because the mean value (3.16) is higher than the midpoint of 3.0. This frequency distribution was corroborated by the mean and standard deviation ($X = 3.16$, $SD = 1.332$).

As shown in Table 2, respondents were investigated whether heavy dependence on initiatives funded by foreign donors like UNICEF and USAID militating against challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration and management of primary healthcare system in the study area, respondents, in reacting to this comment gave a diverse opinion on the assertion, 61 (20.4%) of the respondents and 125 representing 41.8% of the respondents were observed to have strongly agreed and agreed respectively with this assertion, 34 (11.1%) the respondents and 72 (24.1%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively with the assertion. By implication, it is concluded that heavy dependence on initiatives funded by foreign donors like UNICEF and USAID militates against challenges confronting the intergovernmental collaboration and management of the primary healthcare system in the study area. This frequency distribution was corroborated by the mean and standard deviation ($X = 3.24$, $SD = 1.283$).

Discussion of Findings

Concerning the key management challenges confronting intergovernmental collaboration in their quest to bring adequate attention to the management of the primary healthcare system, numerous management challenges were unravelled. They include: inadequate funding/misappropriation of funds, lack of political will, inadequate inter-sectoral collaboration, and community perceptions of poor quality and inadequacy of available services in the PHC centres. This affirms the findings of Obembe (2025) that one of the key challenges facing state-local government relations in the provision of primary healthcare services includes: inadequate funding, inadequate medical equipment, a shortage of necessary medications, a shortage of primary healthcare workers, a joint allocation account, and constitutional provisions on local governance. Also constituting key management challenges are the underutilisation of PHC services, minimal community involvement, and management disputes between local and state governments. Other issues noted include a lack of motivation at work, which includes inadequate wages, the private health sector's lack of engagement in the development and operation of PHC, and a strong reliance on programs

supported by international donors like USAID and UNICEF. This affirms with the findings of Ogah, Uguru, Okeke, Mohammed, Ogbe, Ashiver, and Aina (2024) that one of the factors affecting best practices and quality of primary health care in Nigeria are inadequate compensation, unhealthy competition among different groups of healthcare professionals, the private health sector's lack of participation in PHC planning and execution, inadequate information system management, and a strong reliance on programs funded by foreign donors like the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and the United States Agency for International Development (USAID).

Findings made on community perceptions of poor quality and inadequacy of available services in the PHC as core of key management challenges affecting intergovernmental collaboration on management of PHC in Osun State align significantly with previous studies, as Abdulraheem et al (2012) found that in Nigeria, primary healthcare facilities were built in both rural and urban regions with the goal of fairness and convenient access. Unfortunately, compared to the urban population, the rural populations in Nigeria are significantly underserved due to inadequate provision of facilities at rural PHCs.

Abimbola (2020) also asserts that the primary healthcare programme was grossly underfunded, and this manifested in the low performance of the PHC facilities. Lack of effective coordination and integration across different levels of healthcare has resulted in a fragile and disorganised health system, leading to diverse outcomes that vary depending on local circumstances, among others, which are challenges that consistently hamper intergovernmental collaboration and contribution towards the management of the primary healthcare system. Balami, Daura, and Aworinde (2023) made similar findings. According to him, Intergovernmental collaboration on the management of Nigeria's primary health system faces a number of significant management challenges, including inadequate staffing, unequal distribution of available personnel, intercadre conflicts, low job satisfaction, and a lack of accurate data on available staff.

Conclusion

The study concluded that the management of the primary healthcare system, the collaboration of the levels of government, has led to

improvement in the management of the PHC system in Osun State. Even though there are key management issues confronting the management of primary healthcare service delivery in Osun State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the study recommended that:

1. A clear and concise framework for intergovernmental collaboration in the management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State. This can be achieved by establishing a set of guiding principles and objectives that outline the roles, responsibilities, and expectations of all levels of government involved in the management of the primary healthcare system. The framework should be flexible enough to accommodate changes and adjustments as needed.
2. Identify and involve key stakeholders in the design and implementation of intergovernmental collaboration initiatives: Stakeholders include representatives from federal, state, and local governments, healthcare providers, community leaders, and patients. They should be involved in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of intergovernmental collaboration initiatives to ensure that they meet the needs of all stakeholders and are sustainable in the long term.
3. Establish a monitoring and evaluation mechanism to assess the effectiveness of intergovernmental collaboration initiatives: This will help to ensure that intergovernmental collaboration initiatives are achieving their intended goals and objectives, and can be used to identify areas for improvement.
4. Enhance the capacity of many trainings to facilitate intergovernmental collaboration initiatives: This can be achieved through training and capacity-building initiatives that focus on leadership, communication, negotiation, conflict resolution, and other relevant skills.
5. Align intergovernmental collaboration initiatives with the strategic goals and objectives of the primary healthcare system in Osun State, and address any legal and regulatory barriers that may impede the success of intergovernmental collaboration initiatives. Lastly, establish clear lines of accountability and responsibility for intergovernmental collaboration initiatives in the management of the primary healthcare system in Osun State. This will help to ensure that all stakeholders involved in intergovernmental collaboration initiatives are aware of

their roles and responsibilities, and are held accountable for their performance.

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